

Studying Religion and Human Relations for National Integration in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria is a pluralistic state in many dimensions: culture, governance, language, ethnicity, religion and so on. The pluralistic nature of the state, however, has not been adequately harnessed to have an integrated and unified Nigeria. This situation makes the various segments of Nigeria antagonistic of one another, rather than being mutually appreciative. This already bad situation is particularly worsened by the federal government's increasing practice of exclusion rather than inclusion which, undoubtedly, would enhance cohesion amongst the various segments of the country. Religion is one segment of the Nigerian state generally believed to be contributing to the exacerbation of this state of affairs. The question then becomes how the study of religion could significantly contribute to Nigeria's integration. That is what this paper investigates. To achieve this, data are collected by simple observation as well as from secondary sources, and then analyzed by the application of system theory in human relations. This is viable because the various segments of Nigeria interact as systems. Elements of religion and human relations as cohering in the human person are explored as correlation for national integration. Religious expression is manifested in human relations, and effective religion and human relations are found germane for the system's stability and foundational for national integration. There is, therefore, the need to inject elements of human relations in the study of religion to achieve national integration, especially in a pluralist state as Nigeria.

Keywords: Religion, Human Relations and National Integration

Introduction

Nigeria is a country blessed with good climate, abundant natural and human resources. Nigeria is highly blessed in a way that people living in the four cardinal points of this country can lay their hands on one natural resource or another to enhance their living standards. Typically, natural resources bring unprecedented wealth and development to climes they are blessed with. Natural resources are meant to help people live together as one big family, value and appreciate one another. Unfortunately, that is not the case in Nigeria. In fact, Nigeria juxtaposed with other countries blessed with similar natural resources, makes apparent that Nigeria could be suffering from resources curse rather than blessing, as seen in the other countries. In other words, it would not be an exaggeration to say that natural resources have become more of a curse than a blessing to the Nigerian nation. This is because, instead of appreciating God, the creator of the universe for the gifts of nature, and sharing what we have with our brothers, be it Hausa, Igbo, Fulani, Nupe, Yoruba or Tiv, many Nigerians live like cats and dogs. In Nigeria, income generated from natural resources like crude oil is colonized by the elite and top government officials to the utmost satisfaction of their greed and selfishness.

Nigeria is a society where farmlands of rural farmers in the South East and South West have been forcefully converted to cattle ranches by Fulani herdsmen. It is a country characterized by lack of obedience to the rule of law, kidnapping and nepotism, communal and ethnic crises. It is a country where some ethnic groups like the Igbo nation are requesting for independence because of their perceived exclusion from government affairs by the federal government, and as well as bad governance. Nigeria is a country where a few individuals decide

and control the trajectory of the Nigerian nation, particularly as it will favour them and their cronies. What happened in the 2023 presidential and gubernatorial elections have never happened in the history of Nigeria. Many Nigerians came out to exercise their franchise hoping that their votes would count, but, sadly to their dismay, the Independent National Electoral Commission, the body entrusted with organizing free, fair, credible and transparent elections in Nigeria, made Nigerians to realize that they are far from being independent as they depended on the highest bidders among the political actors to determine the election results. Simply put, they collaborated with the cabals in the corridors of power to rig the election.

Furthermore, during the March 18 gubernatorial election in some cities like Lagos, many Nigerians especially the Igbo people were prevented from casting their votes on the singular reason that they would vote the opposition. Igbo people were threatened openly not to come out to vote unless they are voting a particular party. Many who defied the threat and came out to cast their votes were blatantly disenfranchised, many hurt, while some others were killed. Thus, a lot of Nigerians frowned at the results of the presidential and gubernatorial elections, and have since then remained adamant on their conviction that the elections were heavily marred by irregularities, and consequently, rigged to the favour of the ruling party.

However, the level of disunity and disintegration in Nigeria could be linked to the heterogeneous nature of the country. Indeed, Nigeria is a heterogeneous society characterized by many ethnic groups with different languages, cultures and religions. The composers of the Nigerian national anthem were obviously aware that Nigeria is a heterogeneous society where differences in cultural practices can generate conflicts and restiveness; hence, they called for unity in diversity through the words of the national anthem. The heterogeneous nature of this country suggests that the unity of Nigeria is not a matter of having one common culture, rather it should be unity based on truth, justice, equity, selflessness and honest concern for the progress and survival of Nigeria. The unity of Nigeria should transcend ethnic boundaries, blood brotherhood, religious and political affiliations, social and economic status. It should be unity devoid of injustice, favoritism, impartiality and marginalization.

Apparently, the Nigerian national anthem, the establishments of federal institutions, unity schools, federal character commission, as well as freedom of worship, among others are measures mapped out by the federal government to promote national integration in Nigeria. Unfortunately, these measures are still far from yielding the intended results. High levels of nepotism, youth restiveness, genocide, poor government policies, as well as autocratic system of governance being experienced in Nigeria today are strong signals that Nigeria is headed towards disintegration, or worse still, extinction, if urgent steps are not taken in the right direction. Similarly, despite the activities of religious extremists and ethno-religious crisis in Nigeria, religion is naturally peaceful and remains the only unifying element that can hold the nation together. Thus, the thrust of this paper is to examine how religion, especially the study of religion and human relations can make significant impact to Nigeria's integration and unity. The study will highlight some of the causes of disintegration in this country. It is expected that studying religion and human relations in Nigerian tertiary institutions would be useful in achieving the vision of one Nigeria as outlined in Nigerian national anthem, since religion is the cement that binds society.

Conceptualizing the Study of Religion and Human Relations

Religion is an institution that provides the supernatural laws necessary for peaceful coexistence in the society. It is the concept that delineates the relationship between man and God, the creator and sustainer of the universe. Religion is the "sum total of truths and duties by which man's relation to God is established."¹ It is man's awareness of the existence of a supernatural being that is greater than man, and as a result, man strives to establish a cordial relationship with him through worship, prayers, sacrifice and effective religion and human relations². Indeed, the concept of religion or religious system is concerned with man's relationship with the Supreme Being and other supernatural forces. Its horizontal dimension portrays man's relationship with one another; a relationship influenced by vertical dimension or the traditions of various religious groups in the society. Vividly, religion is a system that guides human interaction for wholeness of individuals and communities.³ In other words; human relations are essential aspects of religion that bring out the social function of religion in society. It promotes the

integrative function of religion in interpersonal and communal relationships. In fact, “there can be no meaningful human relations without the spiritual or abstract qualities that religion offers. Human relations are nothing but an extension of religion.”⁴ Furthermore, the concept of religion and human relations is to lay emphasis on the communal aspect of religion and to indicate that religion is a social function. Indeed, religion plays the social function of providing solution to social problems in society. It has been rightly defined religion as “a system of beliefs and practices by which a group of people struggle with these ultimate problems of human life.”⁵ Religion addresses the problem of human existence. It plays important role in settling disputes and ensuring unity in society. Religion plays important role in social cohesion. It is “a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, uniting into a single moral community all those who adhere to those beliefs and practices”⁶. In other words, religion is a concept that binds people together into a moral community for the good of all aspects of the society. It contributes immensely to the integration of the whole society.

Similarly, human relations involve all types of interactions among people-their conflicts, cooperative efforts, and group relationship.⁷ They stated further that it is the study of why our beliefs, attitudes, and behaviour sometimes cause relationship problems in our personal lives, in work-related situations and social gatherings. They are explicit in stating that human relations involve the management of three types of relationships. The first area to manage is intrapersonal relationship, that is, relationship with oneself. This is essential because a lot of people carry around a set of ideas and feelings about themselves that are self-deprecating and, oftentimes, inaccurate. People who are under this category find it difficult to maintain a good relationship with others. They need to be enlightened on the importance of high self-esteem. The second type of relationship is interpersonal relationship, that is, one-to-one relationships which form a huge part of our daily experiences. As a result of differences in culture, most people find it difficult to maintain a good relationship with another person, hence, the need for studying human relations skills. The third one is the management of social relationships which refers to relationships with members of a group. This type of relationship is necessary for team building, teamwork, as well as in maintaining communal and inter-communal relationships.

Furthermore, human relation is the skill or ability to work effectively with other people; it includes a desire to understand others, their needs and weaknesses, their talents and abilities.⁸ They emphasized that the study of human relations helps us to be aware of our human rights, and to respect and protect the rights of others. Human relations skills enable an individual to secure a job and enjoy it. It enables them become productive at it, and also be able to stay longer with better chances for advancement. The study of religion and human relations is the study of integrative functions of religion. It is the study that exposes students to the role of religion in bringing all the elements of society together for the good of man and society. In a nut shell, religion “acts as cement holding our societies together and provides the necessary support and stability for our societies.”⁹ This suggests that the study of religion and human relations is the study that portrays the role of religion as the hub through which society exists. It provides the laws that regulate group interactions in the social institutions in Nigeria. It helps us to analyze human behaviour, identify preventive strategies for interpersonal and group conflicts, engage in resolution of behavioral problems and work on ourselves for self-development. It is the study of religious principles essential for sound intrapersonal, interpersonal and communal/social relationships. The study of religion is the study of the principles necessary to develop religious personality, live a meaningful life and promote peace and unity in society. It exposes students to skills necessary for effective human relations such as communication skills, self-acceptance, high self-esteem, team-spirit, respect for human rights, and religious and cultural tolerance.

Conceptualizing National Integration

National integration is a process of bringing people of different cultures and worldviews together for national unity and development. It is the awareness that though we belong to different cultures, religions and speak different languages, we are one big family with the responsibility of respecting and protecting each other for unity and survival of the family. National integration in a heterogeneous society is often an onerous task that

involves elimination of vices like inequality, marginalization, ethnocentrism and nepotism, while strengthening solidarity and unity in diversity. It is the unity of the different ethnic nationalities that make up the country Nigeria. It involves the concept of “united we stand, divided we fall.”

National integration is often a conscious agenda of the state which they execute by establishing policies that will encourage individual and group allegiance to the state and its institutions, as opposed to sub-national ethnic or other group loyalties.¹⁰ The policies are aimed at creating patriotic citizens out of desperate and, often, antagonistic groups. Also, national integration is seen as national unity.¹¹ In other words, it is the process of achieving unity in diversity which covers the idea of unifying or uniting all forces in a country for nation building. It has been observed that “in Nigeria, national integration is a specific problem that creates a sense of territorial nationality to eliminate subordinate parochial loyalties.”¹² They added that national integration is a concept that presumed the existence of an ethnic plural society in which every group is characterized by its own language or other cultural qualities that must be regulated for common good. Accordingly, national integration denotes the process of bringing diverse cultural and social groups in a society into a single moral community that would provide the consciousness of one indivisible nation. This process aims at creating awareness that all the tribes and ethnic groups in Nigeria are one indivisible entity that can thrive if peaceful coexistence is enabled.

Theoretical Framework

System Theory

System theory is a theory that views the organization as an open system made up of interrelated and interdependent parts that interact as sub-system for the good of the system at large. System theory is a theory that has adherents in many different fields.¹³ Some of the contributors to system theory are Chester Bernard, Herbert Simon, Niklas Luhmann and Walter Buckley. Vilfredo Pareto, a French-Italian, was the father of the social systems approach to organization and management. He viewed society as an intricate cluster of interdependent units or elements, that is, as a social system with many subsystems. System theory is interested in the varied relationships of the many aspects of the social world, and thus, operates against piecemeal analyses of the society.¹⁴

Among the many ideas of Pareto was the tendency of social systems to seek equilibrium upon being disturbed by outside or inside influence. To understand the nature of system theory, it is pertinent to note that a system is complex elements in interaction. A system may be open or closed. An open system is related to and exchanges matter with its environment, while a closed system is not related to, neither does it exchange matter with its environment. A closed system is characterized by an increase in entropy, while open systems tend towards the steady state. Simply put, “all systems, except the smallest have sub-systems and all but the largest have supra-systems, which are their environment.”¹⁵ Moreover, each of the system or subsystem has a boundary, and there is more interaction among units within a boundary than among units outside the boundary. The environment of a system, subsystem or supra-system is everything external to its boundary. On the other hand, social system theory generally deals with open systems because it is virtually impossible to envisage a social system, such as a school, which does not interact with its environment.¹⁶

Vividly, some important characteristics of system theory are: organizational equilibrium-this implies that every system works harder to maintain a dynamic equilibrium. In doing so, it will resist a disturbance if it can adjust to it; feedback- this involves the input from the environment to system telling it how it is doing as a result of its output to the environment. Feedback is the means by which the organization, system or sub-system learns. System theory has the characteristic of synergy. Synergy here means that the collective output of the whole systems is greater than the sum of output of its sub-systems. Entropy is a state of chaos. It implies that every system produces entropy, but at a minimal rate when the system is in dynamic equilibrium.¹⁷ It is also important to note that when a system, especially open system, is under strain and its components cannot bring it back into a dynamic equilibrium, the system may collapse. This implies that sub-systems or parts of a system or society are in the best position to ensure social order in the society. Open systems can easily combat entropy and remain in

a dynamic equilibrium state by exchanging matter and energy with their environment, while closed systems are isolated from environment, and, therefore tend towards entropy, a state of death. This ushers in the next feature of open system theory called negentropy.¹⁸

Negentropy is the tendency of an open living system to combat death or entropy. Thus, the social system maintains a dynamic equilibrium by negentropy inputs from its environment in the form of feedback needed for survival. This theory is highly essential in identifying the root of disunity, chaos or conflict in a system. It makes us to be aware that disruption of a sub-system can damage the entire system. It also puts us on guard against the strong tendency to ascribe phenomena to a single causative factor. For instance, if the engine system of a motor car fails to function well, we can use the system theory approach to solve the problem by examining the subsystems that are connected with the engine systems, example the ignition system, fuel system and exhaust system. A careful examination of these sub-systems would help to identify the causes of the engine problem and to solve the problem.¹⁹

This theory is apt for this study since Nigeria is a society that is made up of sub-systems such as the various ethnic groups and institutions like political system, educational, family, and religious systems. Also in Nigeria, the entropy, which is one of the characteristics of system theory, is made manifest in ethnic clashes, nepotism and favoritism as well as bad governance, and this calls for national integration to prevent Nigeria from going on extinction. Taking a system's theory approach, it is the duty of the sub-systems to combat disorganization or entropy in a system, and bring it back to a state of dynamic equilibrium by negentropy inputs from its environment in the form of feedback needed for survival. This brings us to the aim of this study, which is studying religion and human relations for Nigeria's integration. Religion as a system is the cement that binds society; therefore, it is the best sub-system that can promote national integration in Nigeria. Religion as a concept covers both horizontal and vertical relationships. It is an open system characterized by sub-systems such as children ministry, youth ministry, women and men ministries. It also has external bodies such as inter-religious associations, ecumenical centres, and Christian Association of Nigeria, and other social institutions as it is the sub-system that provides laws that regulate other systems which may be regarded as its supra-system or environment.

In furtherance to the above, religion, as an open system, relates and exchanges matter with its environment to ensure the survival of the system or society. In fact, the essence of this interaction is to maintain the vertical and horizontal dimensions of relationships needed for harmonious living and integration in society. Also, system theory is applicable to this study in that it puts us on guard against the strong tendency to ascribe phenomena to a single causative factor. This implies that a thorough examination of the sub-systems in Nigeria would help to identify the cause(s) of disintegration in Nigeria, and subsequently, helps in solving the problem. In other words, a careful study of the causes of disunity as well as measures adopted for Nigeria's integration which have not yielded the desired result would help to highlight the essence of studying religion and human relations for Nigeria's integration. The theory also helps us to be aware that a disruption of a sub-system can damage the entire system, and this explains the reason for the anomalies experienced in other aspects of the society.

Causes of Disunity in Nigeria

Working on Nigeria's integration is not an easy task. This is as a result of the heterogeneous nature of Nigeria. However, one should bear in mind that it is a task that involves the Nigerian government and the people of different ethnic groups in the country since national integration covers the idea of "united we stand divided will fall." Some of the causes of disunity in Nigeria are:

Ethno-Religious Crisis: Ethnic crisis in Nigeria is one of the major problems to Nigeria's integration. Nigeria is a country of over 250 ethnic groups with different cultures, religions, world views and languages. The ethnic groups, in one way or the other, strive to maintain their identity and this always results in crisis. All the ethnic groups have one or two religions peculiar to them. Thus, it is difficult to separate ethnic conflict from religious conflict in Nigeria. In fact, Muslims have no distinction between religious and ethnic conflicts in Nigeria. The

ethnic crises in Nigeria have also been attributed to lack of trust and sincerity on the part of citizens. A Hausa man is always afraid of Igbo man, while Yoruba people are known for being unreliable. The Fulani people have also become a threat to other tribes. These types of perceptions make Nigeria's integration very difficult. It has been observed that political gladiators in this country also manipulate ethnic groups to achieve their political ambitions, thereby subjecting the country to a state of continuous ethno-religious crisis which impedes Nigeria's integration. Indeed, ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria have engendered more serious violence and disunity in Nigeria than any other form of communal instability,²⁰ and in most cases the conflicts are sponsored by religious extremists within Nigeria's political leadership.

Cultural Ethnocentrism: Ethnocentric phenomenon is described as "one in which one's own group is the center of everything and all others are second-rated with reference to it."²¹ Ethnocentrism makes people to believe that their own way of life is the best while other people's own are secondary. In Nigeria, individual ethnic groups such as Igbo, Hausa and Yoruba hold the belief that they are the real Nigerians and as such, be given priority in everything concerning Nigeria. Reflecting on the state policies, practices and official pronouncements, it appears that Nigerian government is a patron of Christianity and Islam. Importantly, having selected these two religions for recognition, that it would be impossible for the state to maintain neutrality in matters relating to religion.²² Therefore, cultural ethnocentrism is one of the biggest challenges to Nigeria's integration.

Economic Factors: This involves marginalization, inequitable distribution of national income, alienation, unemployment and poverty. There is a common saying that "a hungry man is an angry man". In other words, national integration will remain an illusion in Nigeria as long as many citizens find it difficult to enjoy the basic needs of life such as food, clothing and shelter. The gap between the rich and the poor is upsetting. The poor feel neglected, dejected, oppressed, dehumanized and segregated, while the rich get richer every day. In Nigeria, many people are living in abject poverty while a few, particularly the political class, are living in a flagrant show of affluence. Therefore, Nigeria's integration will remain elusive if some segments of the nation continue to enjoy among themselves the national income meant for all the groups.

Bad Governance: The achievement of national integration in this country is a matter of a just and impartial government for all citizens. There must be equilibrium between a powerful and prosperous modern state and concern for their liberty.²⁵ The government of Nigeria must move away from nepotism, alienation, favoritism, injustice, genocide, corruption and disobedience to the rule of law for national integration to be achievable. It has been observed that out of the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria, namely: the Igbo, the Hausa-Fulani and the Yoruba, the Hausa-Fulani is the dominant group which has been in control of the federal power structure for many years.²⁴ In fact, they are still in power and have refused to allow power shift to other ethnic groups, especially people of Igbo extraction. The aftermath of the 2023 presidential election in this country is an indication that Nigeria government is innately corrupt. It is a pointer that Nigeria is a place where political leaders are above the rule of law. It is a country where a body that is supposedly 'independent' makes a public display of their 'dependence' on certain individuals for selfish gains, thereby making true the popular saying "he who pays the piper dictates the tune." It is a country where votes of the citizens have no influence in choosing their own leaders. This is a serious challenge to the vision of a nation bound in freedom, peace and unity as stated in the national anthem. Therefore, bad governance is a serious obstacle to Nigeria's integration. The dream of national integration would become a reality when her leaders become fair, transparent and sincere in piloting the affairs of the nation.

Measures for National Integration in Nigeria

The Federal government of Nigeria has applied a lot of measures for the purpose of national integration. Establishments of institutions such as Federal Character Commission, Unity Schools, National Orientation Agency, National Youth Service Corps, as well as the national anthem and pledge are measures mapped out by the federal government to promote unity and ethnic integration in Nigeria. Precisely, some of these measures are highlighted in the following way:

Establishment of Federal Institutions: The federal government of Nigeria established unity schools and federal tertiary institutions to bring the various ethnic groups in Nigeria together. The federal institutions are sited in all the states of the federation, comprising of students and staff from different ethnicities in the country. This is in the bid to create awareness in these young adults that they belong to one nation despite the differences in cultures, religions and language. The federal institutions were aimed to serve as platforms for children and youths from different ethnic groups to come together and interrelate, and understand that there is unity in diversity, and also become aware of the need to advance Nigeria as a single, functional entity with a level playing ground for all her citizens irrespective of ethnic, religious or political affiliations. Similarly, Federal Common Entrance Examination, National Examination Council, West Africa examination Council and Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board are all geared towards national integration in the country Nigeria.

N.Y.S.C. Programme: The establishment of National Youth Service Corps (N.Y.S.C) is another move towards national integration in Nigeria. The N.Y.S.C programme established by federal government of Nigeria has helped in integrating members of different ethnic groups. The programme has produced many inter-religious marriages that promote national integration in Nigeria. The programme has equally made most Nigerian youths and universities graduates to travel to different parts of the country in order to experience the diverse lifestyles of the Nigerian people. The programme exposes the youths to the beauty of Nigeria in terms of natural and human resources. It offers them the opportunity to mix up with people of different cultures and integrate with them. Unfortunately, the security challenges we have in the country are trying to paralyze the programme.

National Policy on Education: Another means of enhancing national integration in Nigeria is through the national policy on education. The philosophy and goals of education in Nigeria are aimed at achieving national integration. No policy on education can be formulated without first identifying the overall philosophy and goals of the nation. According to national policy on education the overall philosophy of Nigeria is to: live in unity and harmony as one indivisible, indissoluble, democratic and sovereign nation founded on the principles of freedom, equality and justice. The second is to promote inter-African solidarity and world peace through understanding. The five main national goals of Nigeria, which have been endorsed as the necessary foundation for national policy on education, are the building of: “A free and democratic society, a just and egalitarian society, a united, strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy, a land full of bright opportunities for all citizens.”²⁶ Thus, national policy on education in Nigeria is based on integration of individuals into sound, effective and patriotic citizens, as well as having equal educational opportunities as Nigerians. Unfortunately, the educational system in Nigeria is not encouraging. It is a system characterized by lack of fund, poor salary structure, inadequate instructional materials and lack of proper educational facilities.

Freedom of Religion: Religion is a unifying factor and a viable tool for national integration. Undoubtedly, religion has served as a means of unifying the different ethnic and political groups in Nigeria.²⁷ Nigeria government has promoted national integration which reflects and encourages multiplicity of religion, evident in a number of constitutional provisions, which guarantee against religious discrimination and marginalization. He added that public funds have been expanded to strengthen religions and forge national integration. For instance, the observation of religious holidays like Easter, Christmas, Eid Fitr, Eid Kabir, among others, is a unifying factor for different ethnic groups. Administering of public oath during court sessions based on Bible and Quran, and official request by the government that Christians and Muslims should offer prayers during national programmes also confirm the use of religion as an integrative factor in Nigeria despite the activities of religious extremists that seem to mar the social functions of religion.

Religion, Human Relations and National Integration

The quest for national integration is one of the major challenges in Nigeria. As pointed out in the previous section, the government of Nigeria has introduced numerous policies and programmes to integrate Nigeria's ethnic nationalities, but the efforts have not produced the desired result. Thus, there are high hopes that studying religion and human relations in schools, colleges and universities would make significant impact in Nigeria's

integration. Some of the ways religion and human relations can contribute to national integration in Nigeria are as follows:

Human Rights: The historical origin of the fundamental equality of all men is traced to religion, especially Christianity, which asserts equality energetically and emphatically without violence.²⁸ This implies that the study of religion and human relations helps us to be aware of and respect human rights. The awareness will help us to live with and be tolerant of people of other ethnic groups and cultures. Therefore, national integration can only be realized in Nigeria when Nigerians learn to respect and protect other people's rights through the study of religion and human relations.

Trust and Transparency: The study of religion and human relations exposes students to the virtues of trust and transparency necessary for unity and peaceful co-existence in any human society. These virtues are necessary foundations to national integration in Nigeria, since Nigeria is a society characterized by unreliable government and agencies. National integration will be very far from this country if Nigerian government can neither be trusted nor transparent in their dealings. Also, it will be difficult to achieve national integration in Nigeria if the Independent National Electoral Commission that is supposedly independent finds it difficult to conduct free, fair, credible and transparent elections. Studying religion and human relation will, nevertheless, help to inculcate virtues of trust and transparency to the citizens for effective human relations necessary for Nigeria's integration.

Conflict Resolution: The study of religion and human relations provides the necessary guidelines and skills for conflict resolution. Conflict is an inevitable feature of human society, but inability to settle dispute whenever it occurs affect human relations. Therefore, conflict resolution is a way forward for national integration. The study of religion exposes students to the causes and effects of conflict, and methods of conflict resolution so as to ensure peaceful co-existence in society. It makes students to be aware and be able to exhibit assertive behaviour in all areas of life. It has rightly been observed that assertive behaviour involves the ability and opportunity to stand up for your rights and express your thoughts and feelings in a direct and appropriate way that does not violate the right of others or create avenue for conflicts.²⁹

Human Resource Management: Nigeria is a blessed country with rich natural and human resources. These resources especially human resources must be managed because natural resources are meant for the good of man and society. Hence, human resources must be properly cared for to ensure peace and national integration in a country characterized by people of different ideas, talents, visions, values and aspirations. Human resource management is the methods of integrating and maintaining workers or people from diverse cultures in an organization or system so that the organization can achieve the purpose and goals for which it was established.³⁰ Human resource management is one of the things that will promote national integration in Nigeria. The study of religion and human relations stresses the importance of human resource management. It provides the skills for human resource management such as communication, motivation, reward, mutual respect among others.

Teamwork: The study of religion and human relations is necessary for Nigeria's integration because it exposes the students to the skills necessary for team building and teamwork. Team spirit is the ability to work peacefully with people of different characters and values. It is one of the measures for Nigeria's integration. Teamwork involves the idea that we need other people to make tangible efforts in some areas of life. Teamwork is highly essential in nation building because the problems in interpersonal relationships are less common where teamwork is evident. Another positive outcome of teamwork is an increase in synergy. Synergy is the interaction of two or more parts to produce a greater result than sum of the parts taken individually.³¹ This buttressed the use of system theory in this study; system theory rightly observed that the collective output of the whole system is greater than the sum of output of its sub-systems Therefore, there is need for teamwork among the various ethnic groups in Nigeria. They must learn how to get work done effectively and harmoniously for Nigeria's integration.

Unity in Diversity: Unity in diversity involves the idea of living in peace despite the difference in cultures and languages. It is one of the necessary elements in ensuring peaceful co-existence in pluralistic societies. Unity in diversity is highly important in national integration since workplace in the contemporary society contains unprecedented mixture of racial, cultural, and gender back-grounds. A deep understanding of the differences

involving diversity in workplace and other related places are the most important skills in human relations. Therefore, studying religion and human relations would contribute to Nigeria's integration by inculcating the spirit and need for unity in diversity to students and young adults.

Conclusion

The study of religion and human relations is a study that provides the religious virtues necessary for human relations. It is the study that exposes students to the principles of effective vertical and horizontal relationships needed for physical and spiritual growth. It provides guidelines for human resource management and conflict resolution. It provides laws that regulate other social systems in society. The study of religion and human relations exposes students to the role of religion as the cement that holds society together. The use of religion which is one of the sub-systems in Nigeria to address the problem of disunity in the country is in accordance with system theory which states that the best way to eliminate chaos and disunity in a system is through the use of the sub-systems. In Nigeria today, religion is that sub-system that can offer functional solution to social problems so as to ensure peace and unity in society. These cohesive and integrative functions of religion can only be available to the citizens through the study of religion and human relations. Therefore, the task of national integration rests on both the leaders and the masses. It is their duty to galvanize elements imbued in the study of religion and human relations for the good of everyone and for Nigeria's integration.

Recommendations

This study is very explicit in stating that religion is a unifying factor that can promote national integration in Nigeria. Therefore, the researcher recommends that school curriculum developers in Nigeria should inject elements of human relations in the study of religion at all levels of education to achieve national integration, especially in a pluralist state as Nigeria. The federal government of Nigeria should make the study of religion and human relations a general course in Nigerian tertiary institutions, since the study of religion and human relations will help to inculcate the moral and spiritual principles in inter-personal and communal relations. The federal government of Nigeria should create avenue for seminars and workshops on the study of religion and human relations. These workshops will be aimed at exposing the citizens both the rich and the poor to human relation skills necessary for national integration and nation building.

Endnotes

¹Igwemmar, D.CO, *Social Studies for Tertiary Institutions*. (Onitsha: Etukokwe, 1989), 127.

²Ibezim, I.G. "The Challenges of Religion and Ethnic Identity in Nigeria. *International Journal of Religion and Human Relations*, 1, no. 6 (2014): 90-100.

³Obiefuna, B.A.C. *Religion and Human Relations in Contemporary Nigeria: The Wounds the Healing. An Inaugural Lecture of Nnamdi Azikiwe Universit*, (Awka. Noben, 2018), 10.

⁴Obiefuna, B.A.C. *The Prospects of the Graduates of Religion and Human Relations in Nigeria's Economy*. (Amawbia: Lumos, 2008), 9.

⁵Nmah, P.E. *Basic and Applied Christian Ethics: African Perspective*. 2nd ed. (Onitsha: Gucks System Int'l, 2012).188.

⁶Ritzer, George. *Sociological Theory*, 8th ed. (New York: Mcgraw-Hill, 2012), 45.

⁷Reece, L. Barry., Rhonda Brandt, and Karem F. Howie: *Effective Human Relations: Interpersonal and Organizational Application*, 11th ed. (New York: Western Cengage Learning, 2008),4-21.

⁸Lamberton, Lowell and Minor-Evans, L. *Human Relations Strategies for Success*. (New York: Mcgraw-Hill, 2002). 5-15.

⁹Igwemmar.,230.

¹⁰Adeoye, M. Nasiru., [Religion and National Integration in Nigeria] (Conference Paper]. Islamic Welfare Foundation in collaboration with Department of Arabic and Islamic Studies University of Nigeria November 20-23, 2017),1-11.

¹¹Chukwu, C.E. "National Integration and Peaceful Co-existence in Nigeria: The role of Inter-ethnic /Inter-Religious Marriages." *Journal of Religion and Human Relations*, 13, no. 1, (2021): 250-266.

¹²Chukwurah, D, C., Nwachukwu, T.S, Nnamani, D.O., and Okeke, M. I., "National Integration and Challenges of Nation Building in Nigeria," *International Journal of Academic management Science Research* 4, no.3, (March,2020):22-28.

¹³George, 232.

¹⁴Ibid.

- ¹⁵Arinze, F.O.M. "Theory in Educational Administration," in *Educational Administration and Supervision* edited by G.O..Eneasator and G.C. Nduka, 134-161. Abuja: International Academy, 1998.
- ¹⁶Ibid, 149.
- ¹⁷Ibid, 150.
- ¹⁸Ibid, 151.
- ¹⁹Ibid.
- ²⁰Daniel, M. and Jibrin, B, "Religious Extremism and Youth Restiveness in Kaduna State: Issues and Prospects." *Canadian Social Science*, 15, no. 3, (2019): 26-34.
- ²¹Nnonyelu, Au. N. *Sociological Insights*, 1st ed. (Ibadan: Spectrum, 2009), 17.
- ²²Nasiru, 7.
- ²³Madukwe, C. I., "The Challenges of Religion in National Integration in Nigeria," *International Journal of Theology and Reformed Tradition*, 6, (2014): 16-27.
- ²⁴Nasiru, 7.
- ²⁵National Policy on Education, *Philosophy and Goals of Education in Nigeria*, 4.
- ²⁶Okoli, S.I. *Curriculum Provisions in the National Policy on Education* (Enugu: Express Press,1991), 7.
- ²⁷Nasiru, 8.
- ²⁸Ugorie, U.M. "The Role of Religion in Human Development," *Unizik Journal of Arts and Humanities*, (2017); 389-405.
- ²⁹Barry, 7.
- ³⁰National Open University of Nigeria, *Human Resource Management in Education* (Lagos: National Open University of Nigeria,2010),103.
- ³¹Barry, 18.
- ³²Lowell, 159.